

1 **Collagen X marker levels are decreased in individuals with achondroplasia**

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38 **ABSTRACT**

39 Collagen X marker (CXM) is a degradation fragment of collagen type X. It is a real-time biomarker of height
40 velocity with established norms. Plasma C-type natriuretic peptide (CNP) and NTproCNP levels have also been
41 found to correlate with growth velocity in the general population and are elevated in individuals with achondroplasia
42 compared with age- and sex-matched controls. Collagen X marker levels in people with fibroblast growth factor
43 receptor 3 (FGFR3)-opathies have never been systematically measured. The objective of this study was to measure
44 CXM in a population of dwarfism caused by FGFR3-opathies. Using the same cohort in which CNP and NTproCNP
45 levels were previously measured, archived serum aliquots from 63 children with achondroplasia, 6 with
46 hypochondroplasia, and 2 with thanatophoric dysplasia had CXM concentrations measured. Results were plotted
47 against age- and sex-specific norms, and standard deviation scores were plotted for comparison between clinical
48 diagnoses. CXM levels were significantly decreased ($p < 0.0001$) in children with achondroplasia compared with age-
49 and sex-matched controls. Temporal patterns of change in CXM levels were sex-dependent. As the FGFR3 pathway
50 was more constitutively active, CXM levels decreased. New tools are emerging to study impact of skeletal dysplasia
51 on growth plate regulation and function.

52 **KEYWORDS:** CNP, CXM, achondroplasia, biomarker, growth plate, FGFR3

53 **INTRODUCTION**

54 Fibroblast growth factor receptor 3 (FGFR3) regulates bone growth in chondrocytes. Activating mutations
55 in FGFR3 lead to the skeletal dysplasias hypochondroplasia, achondroplasia, and thanatophoric dysplasia. During
56 postnatal skeletal growth, increased signaling of FGFR3 leads to a potent suppression of chondrocyte proliferation
57 and differentiation, resulting in decreased linear bone growth [1].

58 C-type natriuretic peptide (CNP) is a small, single-chain peptide produced in the hypertrophic zone
59 chondrocytes within the growth plate. It acts on its receptor (NPR-B) to stimulate chondrocyte differentiation and
60 proliferation. C-type natriuretic peptide is a potent positive regulator of linear growth and correlates with growth
61 velocity [2]. Its pro-peptide is cleaved into an inactive amino-terminal fragment (NTproCNP) and the active peptide
62 CNP. Both of these peptides are measurable in the blood. Bio-inactive NTproCNP is not subject to the same
63 clearance pathways as CNP, and, hence, levels in serum reflect CNP production more accurately. In children,
64 plasma levels of CNP and NTproCNP are high in infancy and decrease with age until puberty when they rise again,
65 only to decline soon after to low stable adult levels [2, 3].

66 The FGFR3 and CNP signaling pathways interact both directly and indirectly in chondrocytes, especially
67 through the Erk MAP kinase pathway [4]. Notably, plasma concentrations of both NTproCNP and CNP are
68 significantly higher in children and adults with FGFR3 variants leading to achondroplasia, while these individuals
69 have decreased growth velocity and height compared with their age peers. In this cohort, clearance of CNP was not
70 disturbed (i.e., the ratio NTproCNP/CNP was comparable with the reference population) [5].

71 Recently, a new biomarker has been identified that correlates with real-time growth plate activity and
72 growth velocity. Type X collagen is made in the hypertrophic zone of the growth plate and is then secreted into the
73 cartilage matrix during the process of endochondral ossification in growing bones. Collagen X marker (CXM) is a
74 degradation byproduct of the type X collagen released into the blood as the hypertrophic zone advances in a growing
75 bone. This marker contains the noncollagenous 1 domain of type X collagen and is measurable in serum, plasma,
76 and dried blood spots [6]. Blood levels of CXM correlate with height velocity in healthy children, including during
77 the pubertal growth spurt [7]. It has also been elevated in the midst of research treatment trials with increased
78 growth velocity [8].

79 As CXM norms have not been formally established in populations with inherent decreased growth, we
80 investigated it in a cohort of individuals with achondroplasia, hypochondroplasia, and thanatophoric dysplasia. We
81 also compared the CXM levels with NTproCNP levels in the population with achondroplasia.

82 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

83 *Subjects*

84 The research cohort and study procedures are as described previously [5]. The CXM levels were measured
85 in the archived serum samples collected from 71 individuals younger than 18 years with FGFR3-opathies, including
86 63 with achondroplasia, 6 with hypochondroplasia, and 2 with thanatophoric dysplasia. The original study was
87 approved by the Nemours Florida Institutional Review Board, and all children had written parental permission
88 obtained. Parental permission forms included authorization to archive and use blood samples for future research
89 studies.

90 *Assays*

91 Samples were collected between April 2011 and July 2013. Serum samples were shipped on dry ice and
92 stored at -80° C. Samples underwent no freeze/thaw cycles before being assayed. The stability of the collagen X
93 protein as well as CXM ELISA assay protocol has been previously described in detail [6, 7]. Briefly, dysplasia
94 serum samples assayed in this study were thawed at room temperature, vortexed, and diluted 1:200 in CXM sample
95 diluent. A total of 100 ul of each dilution was run in duplicate along with calibrators and quality controls on the
96 same batch lot of 96-well CXM ELISA plates. The CXM concentration of each dysplasia sample was determined
97 using the 4 parameter logistic (4PL) nonlinear regression model of the calibration curve using Gen5 software
98 provided by BioTek (Winooski, VT) ($R^2 > 0.95$ was deemed acceptable per assay).

99 NTproCNP was assayed as described [5].

100 *Data Analysis*

101 Data for CXM are summarized as medians with interquartile ranges (25th-75th percentiles). Reference
102 comparison data for CXM levels were acquired from previously published norms of CXM in healthy individuals [7].
103 Standard deviation scores (SDS) for FGFR3-opathy cohort CXM levels were calculated by measuring residuals of
104 FGFR3-opathy cohort data against a nonparametric Nadaraya-Watson kernel regression estimate on reference data
105 (age vs. CXM, bandwidth of kernel regression was 2.5 years). Statistical analysis with SDSs was conducted on
106 residuals from a nonparameterized reference regression in order to maximize statistical power, consequently limiting

107 sources of type II error. Error bars for SD values represent a 95% confidence interval in the age-adjusted difference
108 between reference and cohort CXM values. Significance testing between reference/cohorts was performed via
109 ANOVA and post-hoc via Tukey's honestly significant difference means comparison test. Two tiers of significance
110 were assumed for p values: <0.05 and <0.0001 .

111 Parametrized fourth-order polynomial quantile regression lines (5th / 50th / 95th percentile) for CXM levels
112 in reference data were drawn in R with use of the packages 'quantreg,' 'tidyverse,' and 'ggplot2.' The algorithmic
113 method employed for polynomial quantile regression is a modified version of the Barrodale and Roberts algorithm
114 described in Koenker and d'Orey [9]. This method was selected because of its optimal efficiency in computing the
115 full quantile regression process in programs with fewer than a thousand observations [9]. Quantile regressions
116 accounted for the full reference dataset in male/female/combined without exception [7]. Figures were drawn to age
117 18 for pediatric focus in FGFR3-opathy cohorts. The CXM and NTproCNP levels in all 63 individuals younger than
118 18 years in the achondroplasia cohort were compared, with fourth-order polynomial least-squares regressions drawn
119 for trends. Squares of the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients (R^2) for each regression were included.
120 Statistics were calculated using RStudio (Version 1.4.1103, ©2009-2021 RStudio, PBC).

121 **RESULTS**

122 Subject characteristics are shown in Table 1. There were 63 children with achondroplasia, 6 with
123 hypochondroplasia, and 2 with thanatophoric dysplasia. In children with achondroplasia, CXM was significantly
124 lower ($p<0.0001$) than in the general population. There was not a statistically significant difference between children
125 with hypochondroplasia and the general population, although the trend seemed to imply a mild decrease. The two
126 children with thanatophoric dysplasia had very low CXM levels compared with their average-stature peers, which
127 was statistically significant although the n was quite small.

128 The CXM levels of each subject were plotted against age and separated by sex, as seen in Figure 1.
129 Superimposed on the data are regression lines for CXM levels by sex in the general population [7]. The majority of
130 data points for females with achondroplasia are at or below the mean for the general population; this was true for
131 many of the males with achondroplasia as well.

132 This is further illustrated in Figure 2, where regression lines for both the general population as well as
133 children with achondroplasia are all plotted on one graph in 2A and separated by sex in 2B. Figure 2A illustrates the
134 difference between CXM levels of the two populations ($p<0.0001$). The CXM levels are significantly decreased in

135 children with achondroplasia, especially early in childhood when they are typically quite elevated. Additionally,
136 there are some notable differences between the sexes. Females with achondroplasia deviate more from the general
137 population than males. In males, CXM levels appear to overlap the general population between the ages of 5 and 10
138 years old. However, while that period is the absolute peak for children with achondroplasia, it is part of a gradual
139 incline for the reference population. This differs greatly from the female data, which show a significant decrease in
140 CXM levels for females with achondroplasia at all ages until close to skeletal maturity ($p < 0.0001$).

141 As a biomarker of phenotype, CXM is further substantiated when levels are separated by diagnosis. The
142 CXM standard deviation scores (SDS) for children with hypochondroplasia, achondroplasia, and thanatophoric
143 dysplasia are plotted in Figure 3 in comparison with the reference data. There is a statistically significant decrease in
144 the CXM level in children with achondroplasia compared with the general population ($p < 0.0001$). Additionally, as
145 the FGFR3 pathway is more constitutively active, CXM levels appear to decrease.

146 It is evident CXM levels are low in children with achondroplasia ($p < 0.0001$). However, the correlation
147 between CXM and height velocity is insignificant ($R^2 = 0.14$). This is quite different from the strong correlation
148 observed in the general population ($R^2 = 0.64$) [6, 7].

149 Levels of NTproCNP and CXM in the samples collected of the 63 pediatric subjects with achondroplasia
150 are plotted against age on the same graph in Figure 4. These graphs are overlaid to highlight the similar appearance
151 of the regression line on each. In the first 2 years of life, values of both analytes are higher—CXM more so than
152 NTproCNP. Whereas after 4 years of age NTproCNP is relatively stable, CXM exhibits marked perturbation in
153 years 4 to 8. In contrast to NTproCNP, CXM levels clearly decline in later childhood through adolescence. Although
154 NTproCNP is significantly associated with growth velocity ($R^2 = 0.42$), and CXM is not, their associations with age
155 are similar ($R^2 = 0.40$ and 0.43 , respectively).

156 **DISCUSSION**

157 C-type natriuretic peptide and NTproCNP have been established as growth plate biomarkers that correlate
158 with height velocity and bone growth. Recently, CXM has been identified as a new downstream biomarker of linear
159 growth [6, 7]. For each of these biomarkers, reference data have been established based on levels measured in the
160 general population. Each of these biomarkers can serve as new tools to study the impact of skeletal dysplasias on
161 growth plate regulation and function. Evidence is emerging that these biomarkers are different in individuals with

162 skeletal dysplasia when compared with typically developing individuals [5]. This study adds to the growing
163 literature by illustrating how CXM is decreased in children with FGFR3-opathies when compared with their peers.

164 Importantly, we observed a significant impact of sex on the profile of CXM changes in early life. Although
165 the impact of sex on long bone growth in achondroplasia has not been extensively studied, differences do appear to
166 be present in mice models. Wagner et al. demonstrated that bone length in male mice at 2 weeks of age is reduced
167 compared with females, suggesting that the inhibitory effects of the FGFR3 gain-of-function mutation occur earlier
168 in males [10]. A trend for lower levels of CXM in male infants in our study aligns with this finding. They also found
169 that CNP over-expression in achondroplasia mice differentially increases female long bone growth. This is
170 supported in Yasoda et al. [11], who also demonstrated a sex-differential in findings with a CNP-overexpressing
171 achondroplasia mouse model, with females more responsive to the growth-promoting effects than males. Taken
172 together, animal models suggest that female growth plates are more sensitive to CNP signaling, while male growth
173 plates are more sensitive to FGF signaling at very young ages. Our study describes a distinct difference in CXM
174 levels between boys and girls with achondroplasia. Despite similar growth patterns in both sexes [12, 13], girls
175 showed consistently decreased CXM levels throughout childhood. The precise reason for this is unknown but might
176 relate in part to the sex differences seen in the mouse models. Closer study of serial changes in CXM and growth
177 velocity in a larger number of carefully matched boys and girls with achondroplasia can be expected to clarify this
178 important issue.

179 As a biomarker of phenotype, CXM is further substantiated in this study. As shown in Figure 3, there is a
180 statistically significant decrease in the CXM level in children with achondroplasia compared with the general
181 population.

182 Additionally, CXM levels decrease further with increasing severity of constitutive activation of the FGFR3
183 pathway. This is in contrast to CNP levels, which increase in a stepwise fashion with these diagnoses. In
184 achondroplasia, for example, despite CNP levels being elevated and positively correlated with growth velocity [5],
185 CXM is low. Likewise, in thanatophoric dysplasia, where the FGFR3 pathway is even more overactive, CNP levels
186 are even higher and CXM levels are even lower, although this was with a small sample size.

187 Furthermore, it has been previously shown that there is crosstalk between the FGFR3-activated MAPK-
188 pathway and the CNP signaling pathway, both being mutually inhibitory [14]. Overactivation of the MAPK pathway
189 by activation mutations of FGFR3 reduce natriuretic peptide receptor 2 (NPR2, the CNP receptor) signaling, causing

190 CNP resistance. This study further supports this hypothesis, as evidenced by CXM being low in individuals with
191 FGFR3 overactivity despite high levels of CNP. Collectively, these findings provide biochemical support for
192 increase in the physiological driver of endochondral growth (CNP) proximal to the lesion and concurrent decrease in
193 products of the growth plate hypertrophic chondrocytes (CXM) distal to the lesion. The disturbed architecture of the
194 growth plate in achondroplasia may account for lack of any significant association of CXM with long bone growth.
195 Increased variation in CXM may reflect significant shifts in growth channels, as observed in Del Pino et al. [15],
196 contributing to the lack of association with linear growth.

197 It is interesting to note CXM levels in children with FGFR3-opathies appear to be most dramatically
198 decreased in early childhood when these levels are usually quite elevated in the general population. Figure 4
199 highlights the similarities of the biomarker regression lines in children with achondroplasia as well as the trend
200 toward a lack of pubertal peak with instead what appears to be a pubertal plateau in both biomarkers. This may
201 further support the idea that children with achondroplasia do not experience the puberty-related increased growth
202 velocity seen in the general population. A longitudinal study with multiple CXM measurements over many years
203 would be helpful in further characterizing the lack of pubertal peak seen in these children.

204 This study has limitations. Previous studies have noted that there is a CXM diurnal variation of 26% [6].
205 However, reanalysis of the reference data using the hours of this study's sample collection yielded a lower variance
206 of 18%. Additionally, the ELISA assay is not commercially available. However, the laboratory that developed the
207 ELISA assay ran both the reference samples and the samples from this study contemporaneously with the same
208 controls and calibrator sets and under the same conditions, in hopes of mitigating confounding factors. Finally, as
209 skeletal dysplasias are rare conditions, the numbers in this study are small and, therefore, power and statistical
210 significance are limited. With small numbers, it can be challenging to interpret findings. Also, with cross-sectional
211 data, it can be difficult to determine whether trends are true or from sampling errors. This study found differences
212 between the sexes with a greater variation between females with and without achondroplasia compared with the
213 males. Additional data collection is needed to further analyze if this is a true finding.

214 Future studies should focus on analyzing CXM levels in children, not only with FGFR3-opathies but also
215 other skeletal dysplasias, to further assess how CXM is affected by these changes in growth plate physiology and the
216 potential role of CXM as a biomarker of growth in these populations.

217 **STATEMENTS AND DECLARATIONS**

218

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222

223 **Conflicts of Interest/Competing Interests**

224 CB, ALD, BJ, DAO’C, RCO have no disclosure information relevant to this work.

225 CPD received lecture fees from BioMarin.

226 RFC & WAH are inventors on a patent entitled, “Type X collagen assay and methods of use thereof,” filed by
227 Shriners Hospital for Children.

228 EAE & TCRP have filed a patent entitled, “Assessment of skeletal growth using measurements of NT-CNP
229 peptides.”

230 MBB, RFC, WAH, have consulted for TherAchon/Pfizer and QED.

231 MBB, RFC, EAE, WAH, WGM have consulted for BioMarin.

232 WAH has consulted for Relay Therapeutics.

233 MBB, WAH have consulted for Ascendis.

234 MBB and RSC receive research funding from Biomarin, TherAchon/Pfizer, Ascendis, and QED.

235

236 **Ethics Approval :** The original study was approved by the Nemours Florida Institutional Review Board. The study
237 was performed in accordance with the ethical standards as laid down in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and its later
238 amendments or comparable ethical standards.

239 **Consent to Participate / Consent to Publish:** All children had written parental permission obtained. Parental
240 permission forms included authorization to archive and use blood samples for future research studies.

241 **Data Availability:** Some or all datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the current study are not publicly
242 available but are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

243 **Authors’ Contribution Statements:**

244 Ricki S. Carroll: guarantor, data acquisition, interpretation, writing

- 245 Robert C. Olney: study design, data analysis, interpretation, writing
- 246 Angela L. Duker: data acquisition, interpretation, writing
- 247 Ryan F. Coghlan: data acquisition
- 248 William G. Mackenzie: study design, data acquisition
- 249 Colleen P. Ditro: data acquisition
- 250 Cassandra Brown: data acquisition
- 251 David A. O'Connell: data analysis, interpretation
- 252 William A. Horton: data acquisition, data analysis
- 253 Brian Johnstone: data acquisition, data analysis
- 254 Eric A. Espiner: study design, interpretation, writing
- 255 Timothy C. R. Prickett: study design, interpretation, writing
- 256 Michael B. Bober: study design, data acquisition, data analysis, interpretation, writing

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Table 1. Characteristics of Individuals with fibroblast growth factor receptor 3 (FGFR3)-opathies.

	Hypochondroplasia	Achondroplasia	Thanatophoric Dysplasia
No.	6	63	2
Sex (M/F)	3/3	32/31	2/0
Age (range in years)	8.6 (6.3 to 11.4)	4.7 (0.2 to 17.3)	2.5 (2.3 to 2.7)
CXM Total (ng/ml) ^a	19.6 (19.3 to 21.2)	21.8 (15.6 to 25.3)	4.9 (4.6 to 5.2)
CXM Total SDS ^b	-0.61 (-1.63 to 0.41)	-0.82 (-1.16 to -0.49)**	-2.68 (-4.44 to -0.92)*
CXM Male SDS	-0.39 (-1.85 to 1.07)	-0.59 (-1.06 to -0.11)*	-2.73 (-4.52 to -0.94)*
CXM Female SDS	-0.82 (-1.60 to 0.50)	-1.05 (-1.48 to -0.61)**	N/A

^a Data are median (interquartile range)

^b Standard deviation score [SDS]: average residual vs. Reference (Total, Male [M], or Female [F])/reference SD (95% confidence interval)

* $p < 0.05$ vs. Reference

** $p < 0.0001$ vs. Reference

CXM = collagen X marker

301 **Figure Legends**

302 **Fig. 1** Collagen X marker (CXM) levels by age and sex. Achon: achondroplasia, Hypo: hypochondroplasia, TD:
303 thanatophoric dysplasia

304 **Fig. 2** Collagen X marker (CXM) level regression lines by age and sex. Achon: achondroplasia

305 **Fig. 3** Collagen X marker (CXM) standard deviation scores in fibroblast growth factor receptor 3-opathies. Ref:
306 reference, Hypo: hypochondroplasia, Achon: achondroplasia, TD: thanatophoric dysplasia, NS: not significant.

307 Point shows the mean; error bars show the standard deviation

308 **Fig. 4** Collagen X marker (CXM) and NTproCNP levels in achondroplasia

309 Figure 1A

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311 Figure 1B

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315 Figure 2

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318 Figure 3

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322 Figure 4

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